

Empowerment of Women Entrepreneurs with ICT

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ABSTRACT

By using ICT (information and communication Technology) technical capabilities of women develop their entrepreneurial capabilities & enhance social, economic empowerment. Entrepreneurship has emerged as an invaluable tool for economic empowerment of women. Information and Communication Technology (ICT) is always an essential element in business world. The survival of business organizations are largely depending on the efficient use of ICTs in enhancing their survival. ICTs are providing women entrepreneurs many opportunities to empower themselves in multifarious ways. Vital issues demanding further attention is improving the ability of women to utilize ICT effectively and in particular for knowledge attainment and creation, in personal and community development as well as socialization channel.

Keywords: Women Empowerment, Entrepreneurship, ICT for development

INTRODUCTION

Information and Communication Technology plays enabling roles in socio-economic development. In this age of information society, access to advanced technologies in the field of information and communication has provided numerous opportunities to make lives better. The disparity or the so called 'digital divide' between developed and developing countries in terms of reaping the fruits of ICTs has been one of the much discussed issue in the global arena, besides the concern for 'digital exclusion' of marginalized groups such as women, low income people living in rural areas with in developing countries are

critically raised both in academic and policy making levels. When it comes to utilizing benefits of ICTs, consideration of women is always crucial for both as women are less likely to get the benefits from ICTs whereas ICTs have largest potentials to benefit women. ICTs are being leveraged and/or could be leveraged to entrepreneurship among women as well as to help women entrepreneurs to improve their socio-economic condition. Based on the discussion and analysis, before conclusion the final section would then present how ICTs can be used more effectively to facilitate empowerment of women entrepreneurs overcoming existing bottlenecks and building on the on-going institutional and government initiatives and lastly resorting to some recommendations. Information and Communication Technology (ICT) has become a potent force in transforming social, economic, and political life globally. Without its incorporation into the information age, there is little chance for countries or regions to develop. Most women within developing countries are in the deepest part of the divide further removed from the information age than the men whose poverty they share. However, it is not a choice between one and the other. ICT can be an important tool in meeting women's basic needs and can provide the access to resources to lead women out of poverty. Women work two thirds of the world's total working hours spending mainly on growing food, cooking, raising children, caring for the elderly, maintaining a house, hauling water, etc., which is universally accorded low status and without pay.

Women's Empowerment through ICTs

ICTs have given a wide scope of chances for improvement of ladies. It is a ground-breaking impetus for political and social strengthening of is directly accessing global markets through e-commerce and are using the Internet to support their activities with market and production information. E-governance programmers have been initiated using ICTs for delivering government services; in some cases with an explicit strategy to ensure these services reach women and others who face barriers to access information. Women's are progressively embracing ICT for different business related undertakings like getting ready letters and reminders, delivering report, information stockpiling and recovery, planning, arranging and breaking down issues and options. Health educators have used the radio to communicate information related to women's health. Email, online newsletters have enabled women to communicate on a global scale, resulting in increased collaboration to push the agenda of gender equality. New technologies do offer remarkable advantages in terms of ease of communication, interaction, and efficiency in information storage and retrieval; however they are not universally available. New initiatives have been most effective where they go beyond issues of access and infrastructure to consider the larger social context and control relations. The Women's business visionaries in the Middle East and North Africa use data and correspondence innovation (ICT) for their organizations at rates well over the per capita normal overall. Subsequently, Women's are broadly utilizing ICT in making fruitful business adventures.

Variables Motivating the Usage of ICT

Women's business people are being actuated to consolidate the ICT in their organizations to deal with the tasks. The broad employments of ICTs are changing the companie's work culture. Current and progressed ICT apparatuses are exceptionally amazing in conveying quality and contributing towards money related development and progress. The reception or non selection of internet business, m trade or online networking is having direct effect on the disappointment, endurance, development or achievement of their innovative endeavor. Utilization of ICT has turned out to be important in each business division as it brings expanded benefits through business networking. ICT builds profitability, improve work execution and upgrades work viability in any organizations. ICTs enable Women's business

visionaries to sell their items in the most beneficial markets. ICT in organizations have decreased activity expenses and furthermore improved market execution. Women's business people can without much of a stretch arrangement their item blend and information buys in a proficient way as data on costs are promptly accessible on the web. This prompts decreased specialist's abuse and accordingly, limits the data hole between the market and the Women's business people. ICTs open new roads for instruction, correspondence and data sharing and the attractive aptitudes of Women's business people are improved through preparing in messages, word handling and web.

Hindrances Challenging the Usage of ICT

The principle hindrances in utilizing ICT in organizations are absence of information, absence of access, the significant expenses of types of gear, associations, equipment and programming applications. Women's are as yet not familiar enough to utilize ICT in their organizations. This is because of the social standards and inaccessibility of satisfactory learning about PC. Accessibility of system framework is additionally a significant test among Women's business people. System disappointment and system dealing are the explanations behind the disappointment of on time interchanges which hampers the adequacy of business activities. Women's business people's disposition, learning and experience additionally assume a significant job in receiving new advancements. The nonappearance of innovative satisfactory information additionally represents a test for Women's business people. Language boundary is likewise a significant factor. The greater part of the destinations utilize English as a mode for correspondences and Women's' are generally acquainted with the neighborhood language.

CONCLUSION

The ICT segment is presently a developing segment for work, and a key factor for both national and worldwide improvement. Without the reception of new innovation, there is an extremely constrained extension for the country just as a district to create. Women's business people are as yet unfit to totally tap the possibilities of ICT for the improvement of their business. Sexual orientation hole in the computerized world is still a lot of predominant in the creating nations. ICT can give wide assortment of advantages to various kinds of firms. Additionally, ICT decreases business activity costs, improves efficiency and fortifies the business firm in the market. At the same

time, Women's business visionaries are being looked with bunches of difficulties like – ICT preparing, financing, social issues. Subsequently, Government should think of exceptional approaches and plans on money related help, infrastructural backing and preparing offices in school to advance and build up the utilization of ICT among women entrepreneurs both in rural and urban areas to make them independent.

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